

MATERIAL ANALYSIS OF THE MALLEABILITY AND APPLICATION OF A BIO-INSPIRED CUTTLEFISH FIN FOR AN AUTONOMOUS UNDERWATER VEHICLE

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Abstract

The mechanical properties of materials play a crucial role in experimental conditions. In the design utilization of a cuttlefish fin, the material required will need to be flexible. The choice of material can greatly impact the success of an application, as the material's mechanical properties determine its response to various stresses and strains. The application for underwater use with minimal disturbance of the environment is based on large deformations by rods and requires the ability to recover the original shape during repeated use. Additionally, the material's stiffness, strength, and elasticity all play a role in determining the flexibility and suitability for this application. In this study, the authors were not concerned with the overall force and movement of the vehicle, but instead focused on the importance of material properties for experimental conditions that require flexibility to achieve the desired results for this application. This included the confirmation of additive manufacturing gaps within this specific manufacturing application.

Introduction

In this paper, the authors discuss a specific application of an autonomous vehicle, as described by Kim (2023) in a bio-inspired cuttlefish fin design. In this design, the use of a fin was analyzed for biomimicry and considered in a software simulation. The review of material selection for additive versus non-additive solutions was considered within this evaluation. Including data sheets for testing structural design, areas of opportunity were identified that could be further discussed and analyzed. For example, silicon-poured material is more flexible than Formlabs Flexible 80A resin that is additively manufactured, because of the unique chemical properties of silicone. Silicone is a type of elastomer, which is a polymer with elastic properties that enables the design to stretch and deform without breaking or permanent deformation; this is because silicone has a low cross-linking density, meaning that the polymer chains are not tightly bound to each other.

The Formlabs Flexible 80A resin is a type of thermoplastic elastomer, which is a polymer with both thermoplastic and elastomeric properties. Thermoplastic elastomers typically have a higher cross-linking density compared to elastomers like silicone, which makes them less flexible (Formlabs, 2022). In a design of the fin, there is a base structure that utilizes a wave motion to propel an AUV. Figure 1 shows a simulation that was utilized for the control system and which

showcases the movement of the fin in a wave motion. Figure 2 shows an additively manufactured version of this design intended to achieve a requirement for a cam system to be utilized in the design.

Figure 1. Model of the cuttlefish fin used in the Simscale simulation.

Figure 2. Prototype of the cuttlefish fin additively manufactured.

Figure 3 shows how a direct application of the fin will include rods inserted into the fin while connected to a motor that will allow for movement in the z-axis in a cam-system. Figure 4 showcases the experimental review to determine failure modes and an effects analysis associated with this cam system. Prior to the experimental review there is an evaluation of the material properties, based on the required environmental conditions.

Figure 3. Additively manufactured cam system to hold servo motors.

Figure 4. Cam system with servo motors set up in the system.

Environmental Conditions

To ensure that the autonomous vehicle will be able to utilize a fin system successfully, the environmental condition of a wave motion is required from rod to rod within the overall prototype. This is based on two primary swimming behaviors that are showcased in elongated body theory and undulatory swimming mode. In evaluation of the elongated body theory, there is a conclusion that a wave that increases the amplitude down the body is considered laterally symmetric to enable forward motion. Therefore, in the wave's response, the body of the fish is shaped to minimize the lateral recoil from the motion (Singh, 2008). In another consideration, the undulatory swimming mode has longitudinal effects that are clear on the flow separation and which are addressed with a combination of resistive and reactive forces (Singh, 2008). With these considerations of the swimming behaviors, the flexibility within the system based on functionality requirements for the environment were further reviewed for the design.

Of the considerations included for utilization under water, 30 degrees on the positive and negative z-axis for bend profile and reproducibility were identified as key characteristics. Therefore, material strength and flexibility were considered for three main methods of experimental prototypes: resin, thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU), and silicon. Figure 5 shows one of two models that were used for both the resin and TPU additively manufactured designs.

Figure 5. Model of the cuttlefish fin used for resin and TPU additive manufactured designs.

Figure 6 show the second of two models used for the silicon method. The rods used in the model for silicon were square instead of round, based on the model that was used to hold the rod in place while the silicon hardened.

Figure 6. Model of the cuttlefish fin used for the silicon manufacturing method.

Experimental Criteria

The environmental considerations included testing of the method to evaluate the flexibility of its underwater fins, which were made from a silicon-poured material, the Formlabs Flexible 80A resin additively manufactured, and the TPU additively manufactured material. The testing considerations were based on rapid prototyping for resin as well as the additive manufacturing methods (Gupta, 2010). Figure 7 shows that sample preparation for the three prototypes included a dimensional requirement of 30mm x 120mm for the fin.

Figure 7. Model of the cuttlefish fin used in the prototypes (side view).

After finalizing the standard dimensions that were utilized in the test, the testing method included qualitative comparison of the three different models. This included the determination of the bending stress and strain of each material, which can be used to compare the flexural strength and modulus of elasticity of each material prior to testing deflection.

Material Process and Properties Overview

To achieve a reliable and performant product, the importance of assessing and recognizing the fabricated fin's tensile strength, elongation percent, and tear strength will determine the robustness of the design. Thermoplastic polyurethane is a linear-segmented block copolymer composed of alternating tough and soft segments. The tougher segments include aromatic or aliphatic diisocyanates, while the soft segments are generally polyols. The mixture of tough and smooth segments contributes to TPU's chemical compound, consisting of exceptional flexibility, abrasion resistance, and mechanical power (American Chemistry Council, 2023). Table 1 shows the averages for comparison against TPU specifications.

Table 1. Thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) averages.

Shore Hardness Average:	95	Shore A
Tensile Strength Average	35.5	MPa
Elongation at Break Average:	500	%
Tear Strength Average:	80	KN/m

TPU possesses terrific elasticity and resilience, allowing it to recover its original shape after being stretched or deformed. This makes it an excellent choice for objects requiring flexibility and resistance (Covestro AG, 2023). Photopolymer resin includes a liquid base that carries monomers, oligomers, and a photo initiator. When exposed to ultraviolet (UV) light or other appropriate wavelengths of light, the photo initiator activates and initiates a polymerization response, causing the liquid resin to solidify into a single layer. After repeated iterations of this sequence, the machine can form a finalized 3D model. Table 2 shows the averages for comparison against resin specification.

Table 2. Photopolymer resin averages.

Shore Hardness Average:	80	Shore A
Tensile Strength Average	8.76	MPa
Elongation at Break Average:	107.22	%
Tear Strength Average:	22.35	KN/m

Photopolymer resins provide numerous advantages compared to traditional 3D printing methods. Firstly, they allow high-resolution printing with extremely high detail and smooth topological surfaces. The liquid nature of the resin

allows for complex geometry to be appropriately reproduced in the printed item. Additionally, photopolymer resins provide super dimensional accuracy, making them appropriate for programs in which unique measurements and tight tolerances are required (3D Systems, 2023).

The last material for review is silicon. When casting silicone items, the process includes a master or primary model that is utilized to create a mold into which the silicone material is poured or injected. Once the silicone cures, the outer mold is removed, leaving the finalized silicone object. This technique is normally used for producing complicated shapes or creating multiple objects from a single casting pattern (Polytek, 2023). Table 3 shows the averages for comparison against silicon specifications.

Table 3. Casting silicon averages.

Shore Hardness Average:	22	Shore A
Tensile Strength Average	4.61	MPa
Elongation at Break Average:	535	%
Tear Strength Average:	22.25	KN/m

Casting silicone offers many benefits. Firstly, it has tremendous flowability, permitting it to penetrate small details and complex geometry within the object. Additionally, casting silicone exhibits high tear strength. This allows the final object to be subject to constant flexing without surface separation or deformation within the model. Moreover, casting silicone possesses chemical resistance, ensuring compatibility with various environmental substances (Polytek, 2023).

Tables 1-3 show averages of the key characteristics, such as shore hardness, tensile strength, elongation at break, and tear strength, respectively. Shore A hardness is measured by the intensity of indentation made through a distinct indentation under an exact force. The indenter is mostly a conical or spherical tip, and the force is standardized. The intensity of indentation is then measured, and the result is a Shore A hardness value; a low value representing high flexibility and compressibility, while a high value represents stiffness and a material that is harder to indent (ASTM International - Standards Worldwide, 2021).

The Shore A hardness values for TPU range anywhere from 92 to 98 for stiff polyurethane meant for 3D printing. Table 1 shows that the specific TPU Shore A chosen for the fin prototype was 95, due to its abundance in the 3D printing sphere and its ease of fabrication on many different machines, due to it being stiffer (RapidMade, 2019; IEMAI, 2023; Ultimaker, 2017; ColorFabb, 2023; Lubrizol, 2018). Table 2 shows that the hardness values for photopolymer resin averaged 80, due to the fact that the resin being used was from materials and SLA company Formlabs. Formlabs had formulated a special photopolymer resin that, when fully

cured, is flexible and compressible. Thus, the 80 Shore A hardness is all that was available at the time of conception, though it was still considered stiff. This resin was used specifically as it is one of the only resins available on the market that claims to be flexible while being able to be used with additive manufacturing processes (Lay3rs, 2023; 3DPRINT.ME, 2021; Fast Radius, 2020; Formlabs, 2020; SyncInnovation, 2020; MLC, 2023; Filament2print, 2023; CTFAssets, 2018; SourceGraphics, 2023). Casting silicone has one of the lowest Shore A hardness values, while not requiring heavy machinery to fabricate. Table 3 shows an average of 22 for Shore A hardness. The silicone was very flexible and could easily be compressed or stretched without any plastic deformation. The fabrication process was unique to the other materials mentioned, as a mold was required to be able to cast the final model. In the case of this specific project, a 3D-printed mold was made from polylactic acid (PLA) and, once assembled, the casting silicone was poured in. After it cured, the mold was taken apart and the final model was released. This material was chosen for its ease of fabrication, high deflection, and compression ranges; plus, the cost to manufacture it was low (Primasil, 2023; Smooth-On, 2019; Norseal, 2018; Renishaw, 2017; Yumpu, 2023; Wacker, 2023).

Material Tensile Strength Overview

The British Plastics Federation (BPF) claims that tensile strength is decided by subjecting a plastic specimen to a controlled tension pressure until it fractures. The pressure applied is divided by the original cross-sectional location of the specimen to calculate the tensile strength. Tensile strength is normally expressed in units per area, including pounds per square inch (psi) or megapascals (MPa) (British Plastics Federation, 2023). Thermoplastic polyurethane tensile strength can range from a low of 17 MPa to a high of 60 MPa, depending on factors such as full material composition, age of the material, density of the final model, and the specific material manufacturer. The information on the specific TPU used in this current project was that it had an average tensile strength of 35.6 MPa. This is high, considering it is an additively manufactured polymer. However, that MPa rating can be assumed due to how stiff the material is (RapidMade, 2019; IEMAI, 2023; Ultimaker, 2017; ColorFabb, 2023; Lubrizol, 2018).

Formlab's photopolymer resin had a very low tensile strength, considering it was also a stiff material. Table 2 shows that the average tensile strength of the Formlabs flexible resin was 8.9 MPa. Ultimately, it was assumed that this was low, due to deviations in the curing process and the material composition of the polymer itself not having very strong covalent bonds (Lay3rs, 2023; 3DPRINT.ME, 2021; Fast Radius, 2020; Formlabs, 2020; SyncInnovation, 2020; MLC, 2023; Filament2print, 2023; CTFAssets, 2018; SourceGraphics, 2023). Casting silicone had the lowest tensile strength of all the materials tested. Table 3 shows that the average tensile strength of casting silicone was 4.6 MPa. This value was deemed accurate after testing and was

assumed to be low, due to material casting variables and the specific formulation used, which was a platinum-based or addition system, meaning two parts were added to create the final silicone (Primasil, 2023; Smooth-On, 2019; Norseal, 2018; Renishaw, 2017; Yumpu, 2023; Wacker, 2023).

Material Elongation at Break Overview

The American Society for Testing and Materials defines elongation at break as a way of subjecting a test specimen to tensile forces until it fractures. The elongation is calculated by measuring the change in overall length of the specimen at the point of fracture relative to its original length, and expressing it as a percent (ASTM International - Standards Worldwide, 2022). TPU had a high elongation at break that was not expected. At an average of 500% before failure, this material would be able to endure very high stretching before it would break. In the end, this material was skipped, due to its stiffness. The elongation at break percentage was high, but the overall mechanism was not stretching the fin very much but instead oscillating between a few states (RapidMade, 2019; IEMAI, 2023; Ultimaker, 2017; ColorFabb, 2023; Lubrizol, 2018).

The photopolymer resin, on the other hand, had a low elongation at break. At only 107%, it would not stretch much before cracking or separating. Ultimately, this would not work for the project, as one of the requirements was that the fin stretch and bend regularly. Furthermore, it was also stiffer than originally expected, which resulted in a lower deflection than desired (Lay3rs, 2023; 3DPRINT.ME, 2021; Fast Radius, 2020; Formlabs, 2020; SyncInnovation, 2020; MLC, 2023; Filament2print, 2023; CTFAssets, 2018; SourceGraphics, 2023). The casting silicone had the highest elongation at break of any of the listed materials at an average of 535% before failure. Coupled with its low hardness and high deflection rate, this material ended up with a high ranking as the most suitable material (Primasil, 2023; Smooth-On, 2019; Norseal, 2018; Renishaw, 2017; Yumpu, 2023; Wacker, 2023).

Material Tear Strength Overview

The American Society for Testing and Materials identifies tear strength as subjecting a piece of the specific material to a controlled tearing force. The specimen is normally a small, thin sheet with a standardized cut taken out of the material. The force required to propagate the tear through the specimen is measured, after which tear strength is calculated based on the force per unit thickness (ASTM International - Standards Worldwide, 2020). Table 1 shows that, for TPU, the average tear strength of the material was 80 KN/m. This is high on the scale of tear strength for an additively manufactured material. In fact, out of all the chosen materials, thermoplastic polyurethane had the highest average tear strength. This was most likely due to many factors, such as layer height, print temperature, and material composition (RapidMade, 2019; IEMAI, 2023; Ultimaker, 2017; ColorFabb, 2023; Lubrizol, 2018).

The photopolymer resin had, on average, a much lower tear strength at 22.2 KN/m. This is more in line with conventionally manufactured silicone and rubber products. According to SIMTEC, the typical tear strength of solid silicone rubber is 9.8 KN/m; therefore, the Formlabs flexible resin was able to achieve a little over double that. (Lay3rs, 2023; 3DPRINT.ME, 2021; Fast Radius, 2020; Formlabs, 2020; SyncInnovation, 2020; MLC, 2023; Filament2print, 2023; CTFAssets, 2018; SourceGraphics, 2023). In this study, the casting silicone average tear strength was found to be 22.25 KN/m. This was very similar to the photopolymer resin and double that of solid silicone rubber products (Primasil, 2023; Smooth-On, 2019; Norseal, 2018; Renishaw, 2017; Yumpu, 2023; Wacker, 2023).

Testing Process for Material Deflection

In the process of evaluation for material selection, the development of deflection testing was established. This included the following processes after developing testing extrusions required in TPU, resin, and silicon. Figure 8 shows the development and utilization of the material test fixture (MTF). This system utilized a force gauge that measured in pounds (lbs.), zero gauge, and had an added flat-end probe to gauge.

Figure 8. Material test fixture (MTF) shown with material extrusions.

Each material extrusion was placed into the MTF with the end with a hole horizontally level to the ground. To measure the force, the end was placed into the MTF cutout with holes on either side. When the material extrusion was set in place and the holes in the fixture were lined up with the holes in the extrusion, a force was applied to the set screws through both sets of holes to secure them tightly. Figure 9 shows the fastener being tight and flush against the MTF wall.

Figure 9. Material test fixture with a material extrusion of TPU.

After the material extrusion's exposed small end was pressed to ensure the gauge probe was pressing against either vertical wall of the material extrusion, a measurement could be taken. Figure 10 shows that this measurement was not taken at the top or bottom; instead the gauge face was precisely horizontal along the XY axis to ensure that the most accurate measurements were obtained.

Figure 10. Force gauge position against material extrusions to accurately measure deflection.

To measure deflection, the gauge was held firmly and rotated around the MTF in a counterclockwise direction (gauge on right side of extrusion). The test continued to turn the fixture until the gauge read the desired force, noted as 5 lbs. Once the force was reached, the angle of the material was deflected using the numbered angle readouts inscribed into the fixture. This test was completed for five iterations to showcase an average of the results and identify the optimal material for use. This resulted in an observation of a minimal amount of deflection force, based on the maximum degree of deflection for silicon compared to TPU and resin.

Material Selection

As the experimental criteria were finalized, evaluation of the material properties was used to narrow down prototype options. Additive manufacturing and resin pouring are two popular methods for creating three-dimensional objects, each with their advantages and disadvantages. The three properties considered were accuracy and precision, speed, and complexity. Accuracy and precision evaluations showed that additive manufacturing is generally more accurate and precise than pouring resin. Additive manufacturing required computer-aided-design (CAD) software to create a digital model of the object, which was then printed layer-by-layer using a highly precise nozzle. Pouring resin involves manually pouring the resin into a mold and waiting for it to cure, which can result in inconsistencies in the prototype. The speed evaluation process showed that during the manufacturing process pouring resin is generally faster than additive manufacturing, because it can be left to cure. However, overall speed for resin was identified to be longer, because the model development also utilized CAD and production of the model cast. The complexity evaluation showed that additive manufacturing was better suited for complex objects with intricate details, based on the CAD creation of complex geometries with ease. Pouring silicon is better suited for simpler objects with fewer details. Figures 11 and 12 show that required flexibility was based on a rod placement of 12.5 mm for additively manufactured fins and 10.5 mm for silicon-poured fins, respectively, for required movement within the prototype fin.

Figure 11. Model of the cuttlefish fin used in additively manufactured prototypes (front view).

Figure 12. Model of the cuttlefish fin used in silicon-poured prototypes (front view).

Figures 13 and 14 shows that the additively manufactured fins—using the design from Figure 11—had a greater distance, based on the flexural strength for resin (Formlabs, 2022) and TPU (Ultimaker, 2017), respectively.

Figure 13. Prototype of resin additively manufactured model.

Figure 14. Prototype of TPU additively manufactured model.

The printing details and parameters for the resin model included printing on the Formlabs Form 3 Resin 3D Printer. Figure 13 shows that the model cured well and was fairly flexible and visibly translucent. The rod holes did not empty fully during the curing process, but this was mitigated by forcing the rods through the model, thereby allowing them to function as intended. Printing parameters included the slicer Formlabs Preform (3.22.1). The printer type was Form 3/3+ with material Flexible 80A V1, and a layer thickness of 0.1 mm with default printer settings. The printing details and parameters for the TPU model included printing on the Artillery Sidewinder X1. Printing parameters included the slicer Ultimaker Cura (4.12.1). This included a layer height of 0.2 mm, a line width of 0.5 mm, a wall count of 1, both top and bottom layers with a count of 3, an infill density of 0%, a printing temperature on the hot end of 230 degrees Celsius, a printing temperature of the build plate of 45 degrees Celsius, a flow rate of 100%, a general print speed of 60 mm/s, a skirt build plate adhesion type, with a skirt line count of 3, and a skirt distance of 5 mm. Figure 15 shows that the silicon pour fin—a gain using the design from Figure 11—had a shorter distance, based on the flexural strength for silicon (Shin-Etsu, 2005), and was a silicon pour utilizing the cast model shown in Figure 16.

Figure 15. Prototype of the silicon pour method.

Figure 16. Silicon pour prototype cast model.

Ultimately, the casting silicone model was chosen to fabricate the next selection of cuttlefish fins. The high tear strength coupled with its low Shore A hardness, average tensile strength, and high elongation at break made it the most suitable material to move forward with. Furthermore, testing was done to verify these claims. Fabrication of a fin out of TPU, flexible photopolymer resin, and silicone was done to determine the best overall material to continue to fabricate fins out of. In the end, the casting silicone proved to be a fantastic material for fin manufacture for the cuttlefish fin UAV.

Experimental Review of Fin

The qualitative experimental review included the flexibility of the three materials and their chemical structures, specifically the cross-linking density and length of the polymer chains. The flexible 80A resin has properties that have high durometer, compared to other materials on the market, slow spring back, which allows for material to retain bend for longer, and high tensile strength. The TPU has properties that have high abrasion resistance, high shear strength, and high elasticity. Casting silicone has properties that have very low durometer, compresses well, and can be molded onto other objects with ease. Figure 17 shows the process of the manufacturing and testing methods.

Figure 17. Process of the manufacturing and testing methods.

The test setup included an evaluation of three different considerations for flexibility. The first consideration of flexibility was point-to-point. Figure 15 shows an example of this bend profile from each neighboring rod. This was considered 17% of the flexibility requirement. The second consideration was a 30-degree, full-bend test of the fin. This was considered 33% of the flexibility requirement. Figure 2 show that the remaining 50% was considered in a sinewave motion. Silicone-poured material has low cross-linking density and long-chain molecules, making it highly flexible and elastic, while Formlabs Flexible 80A resin and TPU 3D printed material have different chemical structures and properties that provide a balance of flexibility and strength. Figure 18 shows the process of bending the fins at 10 degrees of flexibility, where the resin fin broke.

Figure 18. Resin fin post stress testing at 10 degrees of flexibility.

In addition, the silicon-poured material was more flexible than TPU, due to the differences in their chemical structures and manufacturing processes. TPU was composed of alternating hard and soft segments, with the soft segments being responsible for its flexibility. However, the manufacturing process of TPU required a layer-by-layer deposition of the material, which led to a higher cross-linking density compared to silicone. This higher cross-linking density limits the movement of the polymer chains, which makes the material less flexible than silicone (Ultimaker, 2017). Figure 19 shows the process of installing the pins for the point-to-point movement, where movement was limited to within 25% of the bending of the fin.

Figure 19. Demonstration of the fin deforming during the bending test within 25% of the TPU fins.

Overview of Fin Malleability

The malleability of the three experimental materials—resin, thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU), and silicon—in the application of a fin that is required to bend at 30 degrees along the positive and negative z-axis to create a wave motion to propel an autonomous underwater vehicle resulted in the identification of an optimal material selection. The resin solution split apart at 33% of the required flexibility at a whole fin evaluation. The TPU solution was able to meet the whole-fin evaluation but, at the point-to-point movement, there was rod slip that limited motion to 83% of the required flexibility. Table 4 shows the test results on which the final prototype was based.

Table 4. Summary of flexibility testing.

Material Selection	Test (% of Flexibility)	Pass/Fail
TPU	Point to Point (17%)	Fail
TPU	End to End (33%)	Pass
TPU	Sine Wave (50%)	Pass

Resin	Point to Point (17%)	Fail
Resin	End to End (33%)	Fail
Resin	Sine Wave (50%)	Fail
Silicon	Point to Point (17%)	Pass
Silicon	End to End (33%)	Pass
Silicon	Sine Wave (50%)	Pass

Conclusions

The overall material properties were determined to play a crucial role in the flexibility requirements to mimic a cuttlefish fin design. In the evaluation of TPU, resin, and silicon materials, the overall considerations included material durometer, print evaluation, and deflection. Table 5 shows the deflection averages with the experimental process and specifications of durometer.

Table 5. Summary of deflection and material specifications.

Material	Material Durometer (Shore A)	Material Usage (g)	Maximum Deflection (XY) (°)	Force at Deflection (lbs.)
TPU	95	9	20.5	4.9-5.1
Resin	80	9	61.5	4.8-5.0
Silicon	22	10	90.0	0.57-0.62

In addition to flexibility by percentage and the average deflection, the solution for the development of a prototype also included material processing and success rate. Table 6 shows the overall averages for the summary of material processing.

Table 6. Summary of material processing.

Material	Processing Time (min)	Processing Time Per Part (min)	Post Processing Time Per Part (min)	Process Success Rate (#/6)
TPU	173	57.7	1.7	6/6
Resin	123	41.0	6.0	4/6
Silicon	1440	480.0	3.3	6/6

These results indicate that silicon was the ideal solution, based on its ability to successfully meet the flexibility criteria without damage to the fin, and preferred from the evaluation criteria. Therefore, the system for the prototype was developed considering these results to have the fins fully submerged with slight movement within the static pool of water to demonstrate any type of forward motion. Figure 20 shows that the material selection provided for the system had the ability to slightly propel the fin with a forward motion based on the fin material and design optimizations.

Figure 20. Finalized model for silicon production prototype.

Figure 21 shows the development of the prototype in which slight modifications to the design for fin thickness and size for additional force forward, as well as an extended base to act as a gasket, was used in the production of the prototype.

Figure 21. Finalized prototype for silicon production.

References

- 3D Systems. (2023, February 17). Stereolithography. <https://www.3dsystems.com/stereolithography>
- 3DPRINT.ME. (2021, August 26). Formlabs flexible resin (Elasticity 80a). <https://3dprint.me/product/formlabs-resina-flexible-elasticidad-80a/>
- American Chemistry Council. (2023, July 1). Center for the polyurethanes industry (CPI). <https://www.americanchemistry.com/industry-groups/center-for-the-polyurethanes-industry-cpi>
- ASTM International - Standards Worldwide. (2020, February 21). Standard test method for tear strength of conventional vulcanized rubber and thermoplastic elastomers. <https://www.astm.org/d0624-00r20.html>
- ASTM International - Standards Worldwide. (2021, July 23). Standard test method for rubber property—Durometer hardness. <https://www.astm.org/d2240-15r21.html>
- ASTM International - Standards Worldwide. (2022, July 21). Standard test method for tensile properties of plastics. <https://www.astm.org/d0638-22.html>
- British Plastics Federation. (2023, July 1). Tensile testing. https://www.bpf.co.uk/plastipedia/testing/tensile_testing.aspx
- ColorFabb. (2023, March 14). TDS varioShore TPU. High-Quality 3D Printing Filaments for Professionals and

- Hobbyists. https://colorfabb.com/media/datasheets/tds/colorfabb/TDS_E_ColorFabb_varioShore_TPU.pdf
- Covestro AG. (2023, July 1). Thermoplastic polyurethane. <https://solutions.covestro.com/en/materials/thermoplastic-polyurethane>
- CTFAssets. (2018, September 18). Materials Data Sheet. https://assets.ctfassets.net/q2hzfkip3j57e/b3bd2c4e7806a612a054765550121eda6109c9da547ac014b0888894da41c41291168aa0b8904202397550edbaa7579d/af887383-b73c-4d9b-b554-6c7fbf25c85a_fixed-datasheet-formlabs-clear-resin.pdf
- Fast Radius. (2020, October 5). Know your materials: Flexible resin | Resources | Fast radius. <https://www.fastradius.com/resources/know-your-materials-flexible-resin/>
- Filament2print. (2023, July 1). Flexible 80a resin - FomLabs. Filaments, resins, printers and accessories for 3D printing | Filament2Print. <https://filament2print.com/gb/engineering/1138-flexible-80a-resin.html>
- Formlabs Elastic 50A. (2022). Formlabs Elastic 50A Resin for Soft Flexible Parts. <https://3dnewworld.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/TPU95A.pdf>
- Gupta, V., Kumar, A., Bhattacharya, P., & Sharma, A. (2010). Characterization of urethane methacrylate-based resins for rapid prototyping applications. *Polymer Composites*, 31(4), 664-672. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.20830>
- IEMAI. (2023, July 1). TPU Technical Data Sheet. https://www.iemai3d.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/TPU_TDS.pdf
- Kim, K., & Redkar, S. (2023). Control system for bio-inspired cuttlefish fin locomotion for an autonomous underwater vehicle. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8015652>
- Lay3rs. (2023, July 1). Formlabs form flexible resin. <https://www.lay3rs-retail.nl/en/formlabs-form-flexible-resin.html>
- Lubrizol. (2018). Estane 3d tpu (Thermoplastic polyurethane) - Lubrizol. <https://www.lubrizol.com/-/media/Lubrizol/Engineered-Polymers/Documents/Engineered-Polymer-TDS/ESTANE-3D-TPU-F95A-030-BR-ECO-PL.pdf>
- MLC. (2023, May 2). Formlabs materials. MLC CAD Systems. <https://www.mlc-cad.com/formlabs/materials/>
- Norseal. (2018, July). 9030-9070 SERIES Solid Silicone Rubber. Stockwell Elastomers. <https://www.stockwell.com/data-sheets/norseal-solid-silicone-9030-9070.pdf>
- Polytek. (2023, July 1). Silicone rubber - platinum-cure | Polytek development Corp. <https://polytek.com/silicone/platinum-cure-rubber>
- Primasil. (2023, July 1). Medical Material - Liquid Silicone Rubber (LSR). Silicone Rubber Manufacturer | Compound & Components. <https://www.primasil.com/media/1180/medical-material-10-liquid-silicone-rubber-lsr.pdf>
- RapidMade. (2019). 3D printed TPU - Data sheet | HP multi jet fusion | RapidMade. Online 3D Printing Service | Fast & Affordable | FDM, MJF, SLS+. <https://david-shapiro-oes0.squarespace.com/3d-printed-tpu-data-sheet>

- Renishaw. (2017). Data sheet: RENSIL silicone rubber. [https://www.renishaw.com/resourcecentre/download/\(4d77d545164649d180196f09efccd0f1\)?userLanguage=en&](https://www.renishaw.com/resourcecentre/download/(4d77d545164649d180196f09efccd0f1)?userLanguage=en&)
- Shin-Etsu Silicone. (2005). Shin-Etsu silicone rubber. Retrieved from https://www.shinetsusilicone-global.com/catalog/pdf/rubber_e.pdf
- SIMTEC. (2022, December 23). LSR injection molding vs. high consistency rubber. <https://www.simtec-silicone.com/blogs/liquid-silicone-rubber-injection-molding-vs-high-consistency-rubber-which-is-right-for-you/>
- Singh, K., & Pedley, T. J. (2008). The hydrodynamics of flexible-body manoeuvres in swimming fish. *Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena*, 237(14-17), 2234-2239.
- Smooth-On. (2019, November). Body Double Platinum Silicone Rubber. https://www.smooth-on.com/tb/files/BODY_DOUBLE.pdf
- SourceGraphics. (2023, February 22). Formlabs flexible 80a resin Cartridge. <https://sourcegraphics.com/product/formlabs-flexible-80a-resin-cartridge/>
- SyncInnovation. (2020, December 23). Formlabs flexible 80a resin. <https://www.sync-innovation.com/product/formlabs-flexible-80a-resin/>
- Ultimaker TPU 95A. (2017). Ultimaker technical data sheet TPU 95A. <https://3dnewworld.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/TPU95A.pdf>
- Yan, C., Li, Y., Li, M., Li, X., & Li, X. (2018). Mechanical and wear properties of additive manufacturing polymers for tooling applications. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 256, 70-80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2018.03.018>
- Yumpu. (2023, July 1). Resilpom liquid silicone mold making rubber technical data sheet. <https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/read/26153296/resilpom-liquid-silicone-mold-making-rubber-technical-data-sheet>

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